

The White-Box Paradox in medicine, its discontents and possible solutions

Federico Cabitza^{1,3} and Chiara Natali²

¹Dept. of Informatics, University of Milano-Bicocca, Milan, Italy

²Department of Philosophy, University of Milano, Milan, Italy

³IRCCS Istituto Ortopedico Galeazzi, Milan, Italy

In the current debate about how to ensure the best integration of AI systems in socio-technical settings, the concept of “trustworthy” is often juxtaposed, if not equated, with those of fair, transparent, interpretable, or explainable [1, 2, 3]. However, as pointed out by some medical authors (e.g. [4]), the attention that the scientific community is giving to explainability is perhaps excessive: on the one hand, if we consider the totally automatic setting, human decision makers are seldom required to explain their motives and reasons (and even when they are, their explanations are more often post-hoc justifications than the actual reasoning behind a certain decision [5]); on the other hand, in the much more plausible scenario of decision support, cases of worsened *automation bias* after being presented with system explanations have been reported in specialized literature [6, 7, 8, 9]. This suggests that the optimal timing of explanation provision during the human-AI interaction should be carefully designed and investigated [10]. As reported in [11], an anchor effect [12, 13] may lead users to over-rely on the first piece of information that is given to them when making a decision, thus hindering an independent evaluation of the case at hand. This issue led us to take into consideration in our experimental design whether AI advice and explanation were provided either before the human decision (so called “ram” protocols) or after (“hound” protocols). We applied these two interaction protocols in an empirical study on the task of abnormality detection in knee magnetic resonance imaging, augmented by relevance map. In that occasion, we experimentally observed that visual explanations may paradoxically make users *less* confident in the final decision (see Figure 1). Moreover, it has been noted that explanations may even mislead users with respect to the most correct decision [14, 15, 7, 9, 11, 16, 17]. This second case has been defined as the white box paradox [18]: explaining the decisions of a black-box algorithm may make it a less useful or more harmful support [7].

To remedy these drawbacks, we propose a perspective of peripheral integration, or *adjunction*[19, 20] and marginalization of the machine in the loop of human action and decision [21]: the human being must be put in a posi-

tion not to rest on the machine’s suggestion and be persuaded by seemingly plausible explanations. Therefore, rather than providing explanations based on the importance of features (e.g., relevance maps in radiological images), further research should be aimed at proving that it is more appropriate to prefer and design supports that provide examples and two-way explanations [22], explanations for multiple outcomes [13], and adversarial explanations [9]; or, even more radically, to design for purposely *foreclosure* [23] in order to have machines to abstain from giving explicit recommendations or categorical advice, [24, 25] and limit them to presenting similar cases whose correct classification is known [26]. These cognitive-forcing functions [27] and the cognitive friction they generate [19] leaves to humans the task to connect the dots and be inspired by the highlighted similarities, by their intuition and by those elements of the case that cannot be digitized [28] and still provide the necessary and indispensable context for truly informed and responsible choices. We argue that this perspective, which we have termed *anti-agential* [18], is the one that could provide support to humans without affecting their autonomy, agency, and accountability towards those impacted by their decisions.

Figure 1: Differences in perceived confidence (measured on a normalized 6-value scale) on final decision, after being either supported by XAI providing a visual explanation through a relevance map (XAI group) or not (NO XAI group). Ram and hound protocols are, respectively, AI-first and human-first human-AI interaction protocols: that is, experimental settings where human had to give their judgment only after having received the AI advice (ram protocols) or both before and after having received the AI advice (hound protocols). This distinction is not relevant for the perceived confidence construct, which, in both cases, was collected after receiving the AI advice.

References

- [1] HLEGAI. Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI. European Commission and Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology; 2019.
- [2] Markus AF, Kors JA, Rijnbeek PR. The role of explainability in creating trustworthy artificial intelligence for health care: a comprehensive survey of the terminology, design choices, and evaluation strategies. *Journal of Biomedical Informatics*. 2021;113:103655.
- [3] OECD. The OECD Artificial Intelligence (AI) Principles. oecd.ai; [Online; accessed 2022-06-21].
- [4] Ghassemi M, Oakden-Rayner L, Beam AL. The false hope of current approaches to explainable artificial intelligence in health care. *The Lancet Digital Health*. 2021;3(11):e745-50.
- [5] Capone L, Bertolaso M. A Philosophical Approach for a Human-centered Explainable AI. In: *XAI. it@ AI* IA*; 2020. p. 80-6.
- [6] Tomsett R, Preece A, Braines D, Cerutti F, Chakraborty S, Srivastava M, et al. Rapid trust calibration through interpretable and uncertainty-aware AI. *Patterns*. 2020;1(4):100049.
- [7] Schemmer M, Kühl N, Benz C, Satzger G. On the Influence of Explainable AI on Automation Bias. *arXiv preprint arXiv:220408859*. 2022.
- [8] Kaur H, Nori H, Jenkins S, Caruana R, Wallach H, Wortman Vaughan J. Interpreting interpretability: understanding data scientists' use of interpretability tools for machine learning. In: *Proceedings of the 2020 CHI conference on human factors in computing systems*; 2020. p. 1-14.
- [9] Bertrand A, Belloum R, Eagan JR, Maxwell W. How Cognitive Biases Affect XAI-assisted Decision-making: A Systematic Review. In: *Proc. of the AAAI/ACM Conference on Artificial Intelligence, Ethics, and Society. AIES*. New York, NY: ACM; 2022. To appear.
- [10] Elmore JG, Lee CI. Artificial Intelligence in Medical Imaging—Learning From Past Mistakes in Mammography. In: *JAMA Health Forum*. vol. 3. American Medical Association; 2022. p. e215207-7.
- [11] Bansal G, Wu T, Zhou J, Fok R, Nushi B, Kamar E, et al. Does the whole exceed its parts? the effect of ai explanations on complementary team performance. In: *Proceedings of the 2021 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*; 2021. p. 1-16.
- [12] Englich B, Mussweiler T, Strack F. Playing dice with criminal sentences: The influence of irrelevant anchors on experts' judicial decision making. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*. 2006;32(2):188-200.

- [13] Wang D, Yang Q, Abdul A, Lim BY. Designing theory-driven user-centric explainable AI. In: Proceedings of the 2019 CHI conference on human factors in computing systems; 2019. p. 1-15.
- [14] Lipton ZC. The mythos of model interpretability: In machine learning, the concept of interpretability is both important and slippery. *Queue*. 2018;16(3):31-57.
- [15] The Royal Society. Explainable AI: The Basics; 2019. Available from: <https://royalsociety.org/-/media/policy/projects/explainable-ai/AI-and-interpretability-policy-briefing.pdf>.
- [16] Bussone A, Stumpf S, O’Sullivan D. The role of explanations on trust and reliance in clinical decision support systems. In: 2015 international conference on healthcare informatics. IEEE; 2015. p. 160-9.
- [17] Stumpf S, Rajaram V, Li L, Wong WK, Burnett M, Dietterich T, et al. Interacting meaningfully with machine learning systems: Three experiments. *International journal of human-computer studies*. 2009;67(8):639-62.
- [18] Cabitza F, Campagner A, Simone C. The need to move away from agential-AI: Empirical investigations, useful concepts and open issues. *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*. 2021;155:102696.
- [19] Cabitza F. Cobra AI: Exploring Some Unintended Consequences. *Machines We Trust: Perspectives on Dependable AI*. 2021:87.
- [20] Cabitza F, Natali C. Open, Multiple, Adjunct. Decision Support at the Time of Relational AI. In: Proceedings of the First International Conference on Hybrid Human-Machine Intelligence. *Frontiers of AI*. Amsterdam, Netherlands: IOS Press; 2022. .
- [21] Shneiderman B. Human-centered artificial intelligence: three fresh ideas. *AIS Transactions on Human-Computer Interaction*. 2020;12(3):109-24.
- [22] Srinivasan A, Bain M, Coiera E. One-way Explainability Isn’t The Message. *arXiv preprint arXiv:220508954*. 2022.
- [23] Pierce J. Undesigning technology: considering the negation of design by design. In: Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems; 2012. p. 957-66.
- [24] Gandouz M, Holzmann H, Heider D. Machine learning with asymmetric abstention for biomedical decision-making. *BMC medical informatics and decision making*. 2021;21(1):1-11.
- [25] Campagner A, Cabitza F, Ciucci D. Three-way decision for handling uncertainty in machine learning: A narrative review. In: *International Joint Conference on Rough Sets*. Springer; 2020. p. 137-52.

- [26] Tschandl P, Rinner C, Apalla Z, Argenziano G, Codella N, Halpern A, et al. Human–computer collaboration for skin cancer recognition. *Nature Medicine*. 2020;26(8):1229-34.
- [27] Buçinca Z, Malaya MB, Gajos KZ. To trust or to think: cognitive forcing functions can reduce overreliance on AI in AI-assisted decision-making. *Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction*. 2021;5(CSCW1):1-21.
- [28] Cabitza F, Rasoini R, Gensini GF. Unintended consequences of machine learning in medicine. *Jama*. 2017;318(6):517-8.